

ORGANIZATIONAL COMMUNICATION AMONG LANGUAGE TEACHERS: A MIXED METHOD STUDY

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Organizational Communication among Language Teachers: A Mixed Method Study

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Abstract

The study aimed to describe the lived experiences and the level of organizational communication among language teachers in a public schools within the division of Davao del Norte. This study engaged a mixed-method design. The participants of the study were language teachers in public schools within the division of Davao del Norte. There were 61 language teachers who were descriptively selected for the quantitative and 10 for the qualitative: ten (10) for in-depth interviews, which were purposefully selected. In the quantitative phase, the results revealed organizational communication among language teachers in (3) indicators; task-oriented communication, informative communication, and pedagogical Kknowledge competence was rated as very high. This implies that language teachers were highly manifested the communication happens within their organization. In the qualitative phase, the study examines language teachers' experiences and insights on organizational communication. The results emphasizing open communication, innovation, effective information management, and nurturing relationships for continuous improvement. Thematic analysis confirms quanlitative findings, providing a holistic view of language teaching dynamics. Both quantitative and qualitative data reveal the different nature of communication, with both positive and negative impacts based on attitudes and practices.

Keywords: *language teachers, mixed methods, organizational communication*

Introduction

Communication involves management activities developed within any type of organization to guarantee the sustainability of the internal processes, particularly within the school institution, as well as to offer manifold services to society. Hence, strategic communication permeates not only different organizational departments but also educational institutions as the latter are organizations that fulfill a strategic role both inside and outside their premises. Effective communication is a crucial aspect in fostering workplace collaboration and influencing organizational performance and decision-making. These skills encourage team cooperation and participation, benefiting both individuals and organizations. Therefore, developing and applying these skills is crucial for achieving better results (Cooks-Campbell, 2022; Díaz et al., 2020; Musheke & Phiri, 2021).

In the southern region of Ethiopia, particularly in Wolaita Sodo, professionals across various fields, are facing significant challenges with organizational communication. Studies indicate that many of these individuals lack effective communication skills, revealing that their initial training in these competencies was insufficient. This issue is further compounded by the absence of ongoing professional development and targeted training in communication skills. Without such continuous training, professionals struggle to manage and navigate organizational communication effectively, leading to reduced efficiency and collaboration. Addressing this gap through comprehensive and regular training programs is essential to enhance communication skills and improve overall organizational effectiveness (Darcho et al., 2023).

In the Philippines, specifically in Cebu, the challenge of organizational communication among teachers is becoming increasingly critical as traditional school management approaches prove inadequate. Historically, school administrators relied on a predictive, cause-and-effect model, believing that by analyzing and measuring various aspects of school management, they could fully understand and control the educational environment. However, this method is now recognized as insufficient in the face of a dynamic and evolving educational landscape. Despite this shift, many schools still struggle with fragmented communication due to regional disparities, limited technology access, and cultural barriers among teachers. These issues prevent effective collaboration and hinder the creation of a cohesive learning environment. As a result, inconsistencies in teaching methods and unclear expectations negatively impact student outcomes (Fiel-Mir & Mir, 2019).

Given that I cannot guarantee that every institution fosters organizational communication within the school environment, this serves as one positive contributory factor to language teachers because this would impact their professionalism and as well, it can reflect on their efficiency in their teaching. The comprehensive promotion and recognition of organizational communication within the school environment and workplace can help support in developing a work environment for teachers where all school matters and issues are recognized. This would lead to fulfillment towards meeting the satisfaction in the school environment which would lead to quality educational services, in general. This study aims to understand, as well as to determine the level of organizational communication among language teachers through a mixed-methods research approach. The findings of this study could provide valuable insights for institutions looking to improve their education programs by promoting organizational communication with teachers to develop more active and collaborative institutions.

The various studies about organizational communication among teachers have been the subject of numerous studies, like the study of Brinia et al., (2022) entitled "The Impact of Communication on the Effectiveness of Educational Organizations", wherein the goal of

this study was to investigate instructors' satisfaction with communication in the workplace, their perception of the institution's success, and the relationship between these characteristics. ; and the study of Diaz et al., (2020), entitled "Organizational Communication Between Teachers and Managers: a comparative analysis of Colombian institutions", This study aims to identify communication issues in two official schools in Colombia with similar characteristics according to the Ministry of National Education, but with significant differences in internal communication. However, this study investigates the organizational communication among language teachers in Davao del Norte using a mixed methods research approach, aiming the effective ways and strategies for communication among teachers.

Research Questions

This study used a mixed-methods research approach to investigate organizational communication among language teachers. The goal of utilizing this research design was to gather both quantitative and qualitative data at the same time, integrated the findings, and applied them to the study problem at hand. By combining the results gathered from quantitative and qualitative data, this study design enables the strengths of one data-gathering approach to offset the limits of the other, resulting in a broader comprehension of the research issue.

1. What is the level of organizational communication among language teachers?
2. What are the lived experiences of the language teachers with regard to organizational communication?
3. What are the insights of the language teachers regarding to their organizational communication?
4. To what extent do the quantitative data corroborate with the qualitative data?

Methodology

Research Design

The research problem will be comprehensively explained by means of a mixed methods design, whereby qualitative and quantitative elements are integrated. As most academics agree, "mixed method" research—which combines quantitative and qualitative methods—leads to a deeper and more comprehensive understanding of a topic field (Combining Qualitative and Quantitative Methods | Better Thesis, 2019). When quantitative and qualitative elements are combined to create a more thorough perspective of the research subject, this process is referred to as "mixing" (Tessera, 2022).

In the study, mixed methods would be applied as the study includes both quantitative and qualitative design. In the quantitative phase, an adapted survey questionnaire would be used to identify the level of OC. Meanwhile, in the qualitative phase, the standpoint of the participants regarding the significant result of the quantitative phase would be heard and revealed through in-depth interviews and focus group discussions.

Moreover, to gained a comprehensive understanding of the topic, this study would be conducted using the convergent parallel design, which is a mixed-method design. This would generate an in-depth understanding of the topic. The research process can be represented by two components: qualitative and quantitative (Schoonenboom & Johnson, 2017). A convergent parallel design entails that the researcher concurrently conducts the quantitative and qualitative elements in the same phase of the research process, weighs the methods equitably, and scrutinizes each data from these elements at the same time resulting in must be aligned and intertwined. (Demir & Pismek, 2018). By directly comparing the qualitative and quantitative statistical findings and qualitative findings, the researcher tries to triangulate the methodologies with the purposes of corroborating and verification. Two datasets were gathered for the research, each of which was given a distinct analysis and comparison.

In the study context, a convergent parallel approach would be followed since the study would start by employing the quantitative phase. This means that the survey questionnaire of the variable would be administered to the research respondents which were the Language Teachers of high schools within the Division of Davao del Norte. This was to identified the level of Organizational Communication. After this, when results for the quantitative phase are ready, the qualitative phase would commence in which in-depth would be conducted for the participants to share their standpoints and insights of the quantitative results.

Furthermore, the mixed-methods study approach seeks to provide better and deeper knowledge by offering a more complete picture that can improve the description and comprehension of the phenomena. Because it incorporates both quantitative and qualitative data in a single study, mixed-methods research has grown in popularity because it allows for more robust inferences than either methodology alone. In other words, a mixed-methods paper adds depth and breadth to the research by combining meanings gleaned from interviews or observation with the prevalence of features in a population gleaned via surveys (Wasti et al., 2022).

In the quantitative phase of this study, to interpret the acquired data of this investigation, descriptive-comparative will be used (IvyPanda, 2022). As previously said, it is used in research studies to produce static and straightforward pictures of events while also establishing the relationship between distinct variables (McBurney & White, 2019). In the context of the study, descriptive correlation will be used in identifying the level of OC among Language teachers.

Consequently, this study intended to improve our understanding about organizational communication among language teachers by using both quantitative and qualitative research methodologies, as well as to lay the groundwork for effective teaching tactics and procedures. As a result, the research employs both quantitative and qualitative methodologies (Arnold, 2019).

On the other hand, in the qualitative phase, phenomenology as an approach to qualitative research will be employed. As defined by Forris (2015), phenomenology research reveals details by pinpointing events based on the perceptions of the participants. In other words, phenomenological research studies lived experiences to gain deeper insights into how people understand those experiences (Delve, 2022).

The study would entail examining one unique phenomenon which is about the outcomes and findings of the quantitative phase which comprises one problem or the dependent variable, which was organizational communication, a phenomenological technique will be applied. This focuses on the commonality of a lived experience and insights within a particular group. This will be accomplished through in-depth interviews to hear and reveal the participant's perspectives, thoughts, and perceptions of the important discoveries and outcomes of the quantitative. This would be done to corroborate the data and clearly explain the study's findings.

This mixed-methods study was conducted in Kapalong, Davao del Norte which was officially designated in Davao Region. Specifically, this study was conducted in the different public schools located in Kapalong, Davao del Norte. Additionally, the researcher desired to conduct the qualitative aspect of the mixed-methods study in the Municipality of Kapalong for it has several private schools that have language teachers' functioning progressively in the delivering good quality education.

Respondents

The participants of the study both in quantitative and qualitative strands were described in this section. The participants were essential in conducting this study as they were the primary sources of data needed in this study. With them, the goal of the study would be achieved and realized.

Quantitative Phase

In the quantitative phase, the respondents of this study were 61 language teachers of the public school within the division of Davao del Norte. These individuals were sources of first hand information as supporting evidence to organizational communication. Moreover, the language teachers have answered the set of questions in the survey questionnaire regarding the organizational communication among language teachers.

Table 1.1. *Distribution of Respondents*

<i>Schools</i>	<i>Population</i>
Baltazar National High School	9
Sampao National High School	10
Doña Carmen National High School	10
Semong National High School	8
Luna National High School	9
Kapalong National High School	25
Total	71

This study was conducted among the language teachers of these schools within the division of Davao del Norte. The Luna National High School, located at Brgy. Luna, Kapalong Davao del Norte. Balthazar Nicor Valenzuela National High School located at Brgy. Capungagan. Kapalong Davao del Norte and Kapalong National High School located at Brgy. Maniki, Kapalong Davao del Norte. Doña Carmen National High School located at Brgy. Gabuyan, Semong National High School and Sampao National High School.

Lastly, in selecting and choosing the qualified respondents in the study, the researcher set an inclusion criterion as the basis and guide in the selection process. This includes: (1) must be a language teacher; (2) must be an active teacher of the academic year 2023-2024; (3) must be teaching in the schools within Davao del Norte; (4) must be male or female or any gender, and (5) must have the willingness to participate in the study.

Qualitative Phase

In the qualitative phase, just like the quantitative phase, the participants were Language Teachers within the Division of Davao del Norte. These participants were included and involved in in-depth interviews. Specifically, the study would include 10 informants for the in-depth interview. This conformed to the suggestion and recommendation of Creswell and Creswell (2018) which pointed out that a researcher may have between 10 to 50 participants as being sufficient in qualitative research depending on the type of research and research questions.

Consequently, the researcher used a purposive sampling technique in selecting and choosing the participants to be included and involved for the IDI. As explained, purposive sampling is a sampling strategy in which participants are chosen because they possess traits that were required in the samples for the study. In other words, with purposive sampling, participants are chosen on purpose (Nikolopoulou, 2022).

Lastly, for the selection process, the researcher set an inclusion criterion as a basis. This includes: (1) must be a language teacher; (2) must be an active teacher of the academic year 2023-2024; (3) must be teaching in the schools within Davao del Norte; (4) can be male or female or any gender; and (5) must have the willingness to participate in the study.

Table 1.2. Profiles of the Participants

<i>Assigned Code</i>	<i>Sex</i>	<i>School</i>
IDI-01	Female	Baltazar National High School
IDI-02	Female	Sampao National High School
IDI-03	Female	Doña Carmen National High School
IDI-04	Female	Semong National High School
IDI-05	Male	Kapalong National High School
IDI-06	Male	Luna National High School
IDI-07	Female	Baltazar National High School
IDI-08	Female	Luna National High School
IDI-09	Female	Luna National High School
IDI-10	Female	Kapalong National High School

Instrument

In this section, the research tools for gathering quantitative and qualitative data from the participants and informants as well as respondents of this study are discussed.

Quantitative Phase

In identifying the Organizational Communication among Language Teachers, an adopted questionnaire from a published and conducted study would be used. The questionnaires would then be contextualized in the current study based on their emphasis and context.

Following the researcher's contextualization of the research questionnaire, particularly in the construction of each item under each variable, this would be validated and reviewed by an external validator, all of whom were professionals in the field of research. Later on, the evaluators' ideas and recommendations would be thoroughly followed to make the research instrument more credible. In addition, the researcher would ensure that the questions in the questionnaire were written in basic English so that respondents could answer each question and understand the goal of the research.

Organizational Communication. The questionnaire for this variable would be adapted from the study of Obispo et al., (2023). This tool was intended to determine the level of Organizational Communication (OC). It has 15 items distributed unevenly to three indicators: Task-oriented communication, Informative communication, and Pedagogical knowledge competence.

Qualitative Phase

In the qualitative phase, it would use an interview guide that contains the grand core questions and probing and supporting questions which would be used both in the in-depth interview. External validators would also review the design of the questions to see if it measures what it seeks to test or if it would obtain the data required for the study. Furthermore, in this strand, the researcher would use this validated interview guide to validate the quantitative phase of the study's findings. Finally, the interview guide would be divided into two sections. The first is for the letter of authorization for the participants, and the second is for the actual interview.

Procedure

From the time the researcher was done with the routing of the manuscript to its panelists, the research manuscript would be submitted to the Research Ethics of Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences to check whether the study follows the mandated protocol needed for the ethical consideration and trustworthiness of the study. Also, the researcher would request an Ethics Clearance to conduct the study. Then, after conforming to the recommendations as per protocol evaluation given by the Research Ethics Committee (REC) of the institution, the following were the stages to be done by the researcher in gathering the data needed in the study.

First, the researcher wrote a letter to school principals or immediate heads asking permission to conduct the study. A request letter was signed by the research adviser attached with an endorsement letter signed from the Research Office of the Kapalong College of Agriculture, Science, and Technology and most importantly the approved letter from the Department of Education (DepEd).

Afterward, the approval of the school principals or immediate heads means that the researcher could start gathering information from the participants and gathering data by distributing the survey questionnaire to the research respondents.

Meanwhile, before collecting data from respondents, the researcher would request a gatekeeper in every school to assist in carrying out the study. There would be an orientation to be conducted by the researcher making the gatekeepers fully aware of the nature and purpose of the study. Also, part of the orientation was that the researcher would give informed consent from the gatekeepers.

Then, they would assist the researcher in the conduct of the study by giving the informed consent form to the respondents in their designated school along with the researcher. After that, the researcher would discuss and orient the respondents as to the goal and purpose of the study which is stipulated in the informed consent form. Also, as to what would be their role in the conducted study. After the orientation, the respondents would sign the form which means that they fully understand the purpose and goal of the study. Thus, they volunteer to be part of the conduct of the study as the research respondents.

After these essential preliminaries in conducting the study, discussed below were the different essential and significant measures in gathering data both in the qualitative and quantitative phases of the study. By this, in the data gathering process, optimum confidentiality of data is assured.

Quantitative Phase

In the quantitative phase, the researcher would conducted the study on a face-to-face basis. This means the researcher would personally distributed the survey questionnaire to his participants. To be specific with data gathering processes, below were the different steps to be taken by the researcher.

First, after the respondents signed the informed consent form, they would be given the survey questionnaire which contains different questions for the variable which was the OC. In the questionnaire, the respondents would not needed to include their names as it is optional. Also, they would be given ample time to complete answering the questions so that valid and reliable answers would be getting from them;

Second, after the respondents had completely answered all the stipulated questions in the survey questionnaire, the researcher and the gatekeeper would completely retrieve the questionnaire in preparation for the tallying process. Consequently, the respondents would be given tokens of appreciation as a form of gratitude for their voluntary participation in the study. Additionally, in the tallying of the responses, a format of the tallying of data would be asked by the researcher to his statistician for easy treatment of the data afterward;

Third, after the tallying of the research data, the analysis and treatment of the data would follow. The tallied data would be given to the research statistician who was capable and knowledgeable in data analysis and data treatment;

Fourth, when the statistician would returned the result of the data analysis and treatment, the researcher would analyzed and interpreted the results. Of course, this was with the help and guidance of the research adviser. This was to ensure that the analysis done was truthful and correct; and

Lastly, in the whole process of data gathering, data treatment, and data analysis and interpretation, it would be guaranteed that the data taken from the research respondents would be kept confidential. All of the answered survey questionnaires would be put in one box with a lock and a unique and strong pin code so that, it was only the researcher who can gain access to it. With these, it was guaranteed that no other person could access the gathered data.

Qualitative Strand

When the results and findings of the quantitative phase were already available, the data gathering under the qualitative phase would begun. Which, the main purpose of the data gathering was to confirm and affirm results in the first phase through in-depth interviews. In this phase, the researcher would followed the following procedures:

First, since the respondents already signed the informed consent before the conduct of the quantitative phase, the researcher would now choose 10 participants from the same sample to be part of the in-depth interview. In the selection process, the researcher would seeked the assistance of the gatekeeper. Then, the gatekeeper would be guided on who were the qualified participants to be included in the interview based on the set inclusion criteria of the researcher.

Second, when the 10 participants were already chosen and selected, another orientation would be conducted. This orientation would informed and educated these participants on the next stage of the research. Of which, they would be fully informed about their role in this stage of the research. In addition, in case that during the time of the orientation, any of the identified participants would withdrew his/her participation, the researcher would respect this. Hence, the gatekeeper and researcher would look for new participants and volunteers.

Third, after the orientation, a separate one-on-one interview with the 10 participants would start. This would be conducted via face-to-face and a convenient place for the participants felt comfortable for an in-depth-interview .

Fourth, after the interview process, the researcher would now transcribe all of the individual responses of the 10 participants of an in-depth interview in verbatim form.

Fifth, when the individual transcript of all the 10 participants was available, the researcher would now gived each of the participants a copy of this. This was for them to check and verify whether the transcript was right or wrong. In addition, if any of the participants wish to deleted part of the transcript, or if they wish to add more responses, the researcher would conformed and followed this.

Lastly, when the verified copy of the individual transcript from the 10 participants for in-depth-interview, the analysis of data which is the thematic analysis would followed.

Data Analysis

This section discusses the detailed description of the different processes that would be employed in analyzing the gathered data from both the quantitative and qualitative phases of the study.

Quantitative Phase

The quantitative data would be analyzed using descriptive statistics. Here was the discussion of each of the statistical tool was mean would be used to determine the level of organizational communication among language teachers to answer research questions or problem nos. 1, 2, and 3.

Qualitative Strand

In the qualitative phase, the data collected during the conduct of the interview would be analyzed to come up with conclusions to affirm and support the findings in the quantitative phase. As explained, the analysis of data in research involves summarizing the mass of data collected and presenting the results in a way that communicates the most important features of the study (Harding, 2013).

In the study, data analysis would be done after the process of transcribing the results of the in-depth interview among the participants. The researcher would used coding and thematic analysis in analyzing the collected and gathered data. Further, in displaying and presenting the data, it would be organized into different categories that has similar responses from the different participants. The process was called thematic analysis.

As per the definition, thematic analysis was the method utilized in analyzing and reporting the pattern of themes in the study. Braun & Clarke (2013) stated that thematic analysis was a flexible data analysis plan that qualitative researchers used to generate themes from interview data.

To familiarize the data, I listened to the recordings and transcribed the recorded interview of the participants and keep on reading it to identify similar answers given by the participants. After familiarizing the data, coding of the data begins, I used the coding of the data to arrived at and generated themes, ideas, and categories. Then similar passages of text would be marked with a code label so that they can easily be retrieved at a later stage for further comparison and analysis.

After the codes would be clustered together, I labelled the clusters based on the meaning or relationships shared among the codes. Naming the codes would be the next process involving the utilization of the labels created for the theme and providing a comprehensive name that describes the relationship or meaning conveyed in that specific theme.

Lastly, to strengthen the reliability of the data, I also tap my data analyst who was an expert in the field, and my research adviser for further verification of the data. Then, I would present the findings and interpretation of the data through tabular forms for better understanding and elaboration.

Ethical Considerations

The study stressed safety, anonymity, total protection, and secrecy as critical considerations in order to maintain the confidence of the language teachers. Measures were made to guarantee that these ethical standards were met. Considerations were carefully addressed to sustain the participants' confidence during the length of the study.

The researcher diligently adhered to ethical principles including respect for persons, beneficence, justice, obtaining informed consent, and maintaining confidentiality to ensure that ethical standards were met. These principles guided the conduct of the study in a responsible and respectful manner, prioritizing the rights and well-being of the participants (Mack et al., 2005)

Respect for Persons was an ethical principle that underscores the importance of treating research participants with courtesy and respect and acknowledging their autonomy in decision-making regarding their participation in a study (Munhall, 2012 & Scott, 2013). This principle necessitates providing participants with comprehensive information about the study and ensuring that they have a clear understanding of the research and any potential risks or benefits. Obtaining informed consent was a crucial aspect of adhering to this principle, as it signifies voluntary agreement based on an informed understanding. By upholding the principle of respect for persons, the researcher can ensure that the study was conducted ethically and in a manner that honors the rights and autonomy of the participants.

The researcher sought consent from the participants and planned the schedule ahead of time to prevent conflicts with their classes or other responsibilities. This was done to guarantee that the researcher's presence would not interfere with the schedules of the participants and to eliminate the need to reschedule or cancel the interviews. The researcher built a polite and cordial connection with the participants throughout the course of my research and gained their consent before recording the talks. It also permitted participants to ask questions at any time and kept the in-depth interviews. Furthermore, participants had the option to refuse to answer sensitive questions. It was able to conduct the study ethically and courteously by building rapport with the participants and acting with kindness towards them.

Consent was a fundamental aspect of research ethics and served as a way to show respect to research participants. To ensure the ethical conduct of the study, I would provide the participants with letters of permission and consent that outline the details of the study, including the methods, design, and procedures. These letters were intended to help the participants understand the nature of the study and make informed decisions about whether to participate. Before the interview started, the researcher asked permission to record the full conversation and all the responses of the participants.

The researcher also informed the participants that they have the right to be informed of the result of the study. By following these ethical guidelines, the researcher would be able to ensure that the study would be conducted responsibly and respectfully.

Beneficence, as an ethical principle, emphasizes the commitment to minimize risks and maximize the well-being of research participants. In this study, efforts were made to ensure the safety and protection of the participants. The researcher would locate a secure location where the participants and researcher can conduct a face-to-face interview to ensure the safety of all the participants. The anonymity of the interviewees would be maintained to prevent any potential risks to their privacy and confidentiality. All files of information would be properly secured and not left unattended or unprotected (Briki & Green, 2007).

To adhere to the principle of beneficence, I took steps to protect the anonymity and confidentiality of the participant's responses and personal identities. So, they can use pseudonyms for their privacy. By taking these measures, I would be able to ensure the well-being and interests of the participants and demonstrate a commitment to ethical research practices.

Confidentiality towards the data, results, and findings including the safeguard of participants, different techniques would be used. Meaning, that all personal identities of the participants would be hidden and not shown. All materials including audio records, encoded transcripts, notes, soft and hard copies of data, and others should be eliminated right after the data is analyzed (Maree & Westhuizen, 2007).

To protect the participants' identification and ensure compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, I discrete coding to denote each participant's responses. This measure would involve carefully phrasing any information that could potentially identify the participants in terms of their name, gender, ethnicity, or employment/location to avoid violating their anonymity. By using proper coding and other measures, I would be able to protect the participants' identities and ensure that their privacy is respected.

Justice in the conduct of this study will be upheld by ensuring that the rights of the participants who identified themselves as Language Teachers were respected. Given that the study aims to better know the organizational communication among language teachers, no rights of language teachers would be violated.

To ensure fairness and equal opportunity for participation, the researcher utilized descriptive sampling techniques. Language teachers would not be coerced into participating and were given the freedom to decline if they so chose. In recognition of their contribution, tokens would be provided to the participants, and they would be duly credited for their involvement in the research, contributing to the overall success of the study. Additionally, justice would be ensured by including only relevant utterances of the participants related to the research objectives and accurately transcribing them (Munhall 2012, Scott 2013).

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results of data in both quantitative and qualitative phases. The first phase deals with the quantitative part which displays the status of Organizational Communication among Language Teachers. The second phase deals with the qualitative part which was presented in a matrix form. The matrix shows the responses of the participants on their lived experiences and insights regarding organizational communication among language teachers. Also, the matrix contains the issues probed, core ideas, codes or categories, essential themes and the supporting theoretical perspectives. Further, another matrix shows the data integration of the salient quantitative and qualitative findings.

Status of Organizational Communication among Language Teachers

The results of the survey conducted are presented here. The overall mean, the items with the highest and the lowest ratings per indicators were given.

Shown in Table 2 is the status of the organizational communication among language teachers of the different public schools within the Division of Davao del Norte. It obtained an overall mean score of 4.73 with a description of very high. This means that organizational communication is very much manifested. organizational communication as the variable of the study has three indicators namely: task-oriented communication, informative communication, and pedagogical knowledge competence.

Task-Oriented Communication. In terms of Task-Oriented communication, the category mean is 4.74, which is described as very high. This means that it is very much manifested by the language teachers. Among the items under this indicator, Item no. 1, Acquiring most of the daily communication I receive comes in the form of "directives" from the principal, got the highest mean of 4.84 which is described as very high. This means that it is always manifested. On the other hand, Item no. 2, Receiving the information in most of situations was the lowest item rated by the respondents, with a mean of 4.67. This rating is described as very high. This means that it is also always manifested by the language teachers however it is not the same with Item no. 1.

Informative Communication. The informative communication was rated by the respondents as very high, with a category mean of 4.70. This means that it is always manifested by the language teachers. Item no. 1, receiving most of the information passed down from the management is detailed and accurate, and garnered the highest rating with a mean 4.85, which is described as very high. This means that it is always manifested by the language teachers. Thus, language teachers interact with one another in an educational manner. When communicating, all necessary information is conveyed through each detail to the other. Conversely, seeing the lines of information are "open" to the principal, got the lowest-rated mean of 4.64, which is described as very high. This means that it is always manifested by the respondents. It received the lowest average because the teachers rated it the lowest, despite the fact that language teachers inside their organization always execute it.

Table 2. Status of Organizational Communication

Variables and Indicators	Mean	Description
A. Task-oriented Communication		
1. Acquiring most of the daily communication I receive comes in the form of "directives" from the principal.	4.84	Very High
2. Receiving the information I need to effectively perform my job, in most of situations.	4.67	Very High
3. Believing the directives that come from the principal is clear and consistent which will lead to performing my tasks efficiently and effectively.	4.72	Very High
4. Considering that my co-teacher and I readily share important information that is critical to our success.	4.77	Very High
5. Believing that the principal values my ideas to reach the organizational goals.	4.72	Very High
Category Mean	4.74	Very High
B. Informative Communication		
1. Receiving most of the information passed down from the management is detailed and accurate.	4.85	Very High
2. Feeling comfortable passing along the High information that I receive from my principal to our co-workers.	4.57	Very
3. Getting most of the information about school High news and events via memos/emails/ and chat.	4.75	Very
4. Seeing the lines of information are "open" to the principal	4.64	Very High
5. Believing that my superior provides a sufficient amount of useful information that I understand	4.70	Very High
Category Mean	4.70	Very High
C. Pedagogical Knowledge Competence		
1. Managing the class situation to give the same learning chances to all students	4.84	Very High
2. Planning the learning process related to each other by focusing on the learning process	4.82	Very High
3. Arranging the learning plans related to the syllabus.	4.79	Very High
4. Supporting the students to learn based on their learning process	4.75	Very High
5. Paying attention to students and responding to them	4.56	Very High
Category Mean	4.75	Very High
Overall Mean	4.73	Very High

Pedagogical Knowledge Competence. The pedagogical knowledge competence got a category mean of 4.75, which is described as very high. This means that it is always manifested by the language teachers. Item no. 1, managing the class situation to give the same learning chances to all students got the highest mean of 4.84, which is described as very high. This means that it is always manifested by the language teachers. Language teachers always prioritize classroom management. In order for students to consistently receive the best learning standards out of all students, teachers must put their students' needs first.

Meanwhile, paying attention to students and responding to them is the lowest-rated item which has a high category mean of 4.56. This means that it is always manifested by the language teachers.

The Lived Experiences of Language Teachers with Regards to their Organizational Communication

There are five essential themes that are created based on the in-depth interviews of the participants on the first research question with regard to their lived experiences. Before the presentation of the results from the interviews and discussions, profiles of the participants for the qualitative data collection are selected purposively.

Further, Table 3.1 deals with the lived experiences of the language teachers with regard to their organizational communication. The essential themes that emerged from the transcriptions of the participants' responses for research question number one consisted of overarching themes which are summarized in the said table.

Table 3.1. The Lived Experiences of the Language Teachers with Regards to Organizational Communication

<i>Issues Probed</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>	<i>Code/ Categories</i>	<i>Essential Themes</i>	<i>Theoretical Support</i>
Clarity And Effectiveness of Direct Communication In Avoiding Misunderstandings.	Discussing something personally specifically related to the concerns or issues.	Discussing and Addressing Concerns Directly	Establishing Open Channels and Clear Lines of Communication	Pragmatic Theory
	Emphasizing the importance of holding meetings to address concerns directly and personally, particularly if they are important.			
Level Of Trust and Comfort In Expressing Opinions Without Fear Of Judgment.	Personally going to the office for school-related matters, emphasis is placed on face-to-face communication, ensuring direct and clear interactions.	Communicating with Authority Figure	Creating – Culture of Openness and Respectful Dialogue	Dialogue Theory
	Concerns are addressed directly between the parties involved.			
	Needing to personally deliver message due to inaccessibility of technology or cellphones.			
	Communicating directly with the principal for school related matters.			
	Directing to the school if matter is urgent.			
	Communicating personally with the school head for school related matters.			
	Requiring constant communication with our principal or whoever is in authority.			
	Communicating directly and personally with the school head.			
	Being directed to go to the office for task announcement or instruction.			
	Personally approaching the school head when there are school-related matters.			
Communicating with the school head through message or call.	Communicating Openly and Accepting Ideas	Creating – Culture of Openness and Respectful Dialogue	Dialogue Theory	
Communicating with Master Teacher regarding with the matter, first.				
Giving everyone the opportunity to speak and share their suggestions, comments, and concerns openly during meetings.				
Promoting a culture where opinions are accepted and valued, and decisions are made based on what's best for everyone.				
Recognizing the importance of meeting in person if something is deemed important and personal, to effectively discuss concerns or relay important information.				
Accepting suggestions with a sense regardless of the person's position.				
Considering potential positive outcomes of a suggestion before accepting it.				
Hearing and accepting ideas with potential positive impact.				
Accepting and sharing ideas from others.				
Equal chance of contributing visions or plans.				
Allowing for the sharing of ideas and perspectives, leads to a cohesive and familial work environment conducive to achieving common goals.	Communicating			
Being open in sharing and communicating.				

<p>Impact Of Communication Strategies on Achieving Desired Outcomes And Avoiding Inefficiencies</p>	<p>Not afraid of asking help because of the openness. Communicating politely with colleagues. Communicating to superior with respect. Being open to suggestion and perspectives of others. Being open to accepting suggestions from others. Communicating through listening to accomplish task and responsibilities. Being open-minded and actively participating in meaningful dialogues are essential approaches for accepting information and suggestions. School Head communicates by giving feedback. Confirming the principal's presence in the office through colleagues, and then presenting their plans and suggestions for activities directly to the principal. Communication has a great impact personally and to the organization. Conducting a meeting to discuss information or announcements. Using group chats (GCs) to facilitate discussions among different members of the organization. Using different group chats for specific purposes within the school community, such as for official issuances or documentation, ensuring organization and clarity in communication. Utilizing group chats for regular communications. Utilizing group chats for communication. Being informed ahead of time through group chats. Utilizing group chats in disseminating announcements or information. Utilizing group chats to communicate minor concerns.</p>	<p>with Respect and Openness</p>	<p>Practicing Effective Communication</p> <p>Utilizing Effective Communication Strategies</p>	<p>Coordinated Management of Meaning Theory</p>
<p>Efficiency And Appropriateness of Formal Channels In Transmitting Information Effectiveness In Identifying and Addressing Communication Barriers</p>	<p>Utilizing memorandum for school related matters. Utilization of memo in disseminating information. Usage of memorandum to disseminate information. Miscommunications arise without proper organizational communication. Relying solely on memos for communication can lead to miscommunication and issues, particularly when there are delays or forgetfulness in sending them, resulting in last-minute notifications and potential conflicts. Misinterpretations and misunderstandings sometimes arise due to individuals not adhering to or disregarding memos or guidelines. There are leaders who, in addition to providing memos, personally call and explain matters to individuals to ensure better understanding and communication. Without communication, important information that needs to be understood cannot be grasped Pitching in ideas for improvement or resolution of a problem. Weighing the pros and cons of a suggestion. Accepting others' opinions and not opposing them. School Head makes sure to disseminate information of what they've talked about in their meetings to the teachers under her/him. School Head makes sure to inform teachers ahead of time to avoid procrastination. Using communication to achieve needs and goals.</p>	<p>Utilizing Memoranda</p>	<p>Recognizing the Impact of Miscommunication</p> <p>Addressing miscommunication through Collective Problem Solving</p>	<p>Media Richness Theory</p> <p>Intercultural Communication Theory</p>
		<p>Seeking Improvement Through Communication</p>		

Setting clear expectations for tasks and providing support are crucial for effectively carrying out responsibilities.

Following Direct Communication Practices. In the context of organizational communication among teachers, most participants mentioned that when they need to ask or discuss something with their immediate head or colleagues, they prefer to approach them directly or personally to have a one-on-one discussion. This direct engagement is perceived as instrumental in fostering effective communication channels, facilitating the expression of ideas, and nurturing collaborative problem-solving. This mode of communication not only ensures that messages are conveyed accurately but also promotes a deeper understanding of the subject matter at hand.

Discussing and Addressing Concerns Directly. This is the first code of the probed on the first probed issue. The language teachers believe that to achieve effective communication, whether with their immediate superiors or colleagues, the most preferred method is through personal one-on-one discussions. This approach allows for clear, comprehensive communication, fostering trust and rapport among organizations. This personalized approach contributes to a more cohesive and collaborative work environment within educational institutions, enhancing the overall communication process.

Similarly, Participant 1 stated that when it comes to communicating with her immediate superior about an important school-related matter, she approaches her immediate head personally in order to have a face-to-face discussion with her. Effective communication and understanding are crucial for efficient resolution of issues within the school environment, fostering trust and smoother interactions between individuals. She stated that:

“... personally go to her office. Basta ingon ana kanang school related matter, ing ana jud sya go to the office directly. Face to face jud sya nga communication. And ano, through proposals. Ana, like naa mi mga action plan nga naa mi gusto mahitabo sa eskwelahan, for example ako as coordinator sa English.” (IDI-02)

(Personally go to her office, haha! That's just how it is when it comes to school-related matters, you really have to go directly to the office. It's all face-to-face communication. And, well, through proposals, like we have action plans for things we want to happen at the school. For example, me as the coordinator for English.)

Additionally, Participant 1 added that they will conduct a meeting with their colleagues and immediate head in order to thoroughly discuss a matter. According to her, through this approach, they can effectively express and exchange ideas regarding school-related matters, as well as issues or events occurring both inside and outside their school premises. She said that:

“...kanang importante gyud sya nga if ever nay mga concerns we should have meetings. Para mahisgutan sya personally.” (IDI-01)

(... it is very important that if we have concerns, we should hold a meeting so that we can discuss them in person.)

Moreover, Participant 2 also expressed that when she has school-related matters requiring the presence of their school head, it is indeed better to communicate with their immediate heads personally. She stressed that they can make sure the complexity and significance of the matter are adequately conveyed and understood by speaking with their immediate heads directly. As Participant 2 stated,

“... I personally go to her office. Basta ingon ana kanang school related matter, ing ana jud sya go to the office directly. Face to face jud sya nga communication.” (IDI-02)

(...I personally go to her office. If it's school-related, the best approach is to go to the office directly. It should be a face-to-face communication.)

Face-to-face communication will foster collaboration and sharing of thoughts among teachers, effective communication is crucial in teaching, as it fosters understanding and teamwork among teachers. It allows for immediate clarification of ideas, fostering better problem-solving and decision-making. Direct interaction fosters a deeper understanding of each other's perspectives, fostering strong professional relationships. Active participation and engagement result in more productive information exchange, enhancing teaching practices. As Participant 2 also stated that,

“If ever naay concern ang isa direcho lang jud sya ana. kung silay naay concern sa akua. For example, sa during mga like kami mga master teacher naa pd mi ipaclear or magprovide mig mga physical assistance diba. So in that case, naa mi ginatawag nga mga precon and postcon, ingon ana.” (IDI-02)

(If ever there is a concern, approach directly. If they have concerns about me, for example, like we master teachers we want to clear something or we will be going to provide physical assistance. So in that case, we have so-called the precon and postcon.)

Although technology is present on school premises, which language teachers use as a medium of communication, there are instances when it would be better to communicate directly with colleagues and immediate heads. This is especially true if their school head did not receive the message online, direct communication is essential for timely and accurate information conveying. Face-to-face interaction allows for immediate clarification and discussion of concerns, ensuring a smooth and efficient school environment. As

Participant 3 stated,

“Kung labi na diri sa amoa naa mi mga lagyu kinahanglan lang gyud namo ang paggamit sa mga teknolohiya or cellphone. Or kung walay mga signal, walay wifi so adtuun jud namo para mas mapadali.” (IDI-03)

(Especially here in our school, where teachers are often located far from each other, we heavily rely on technology or cellphones for communication. However, if there is no signal or WiFi available, we resort to approaching each other personally.)

Technology aids the process of communication, making it easier for individuals to connect with each other. With the presence of messaging platforms, group chats, and various other technological tools, communication has become more convenient than ever. However, language teachers still observe that it would be much better to communicate with their school head or colleagues personally. Through face-to-face interaction, they can express their thoughts more efficiently and effectively. As Participant 4 said,

“I talk to her directly or usahay pag wala siya kay gina chat ra namo/nako siya, kay among principal is dali raman siya ma duolan, specially mga school related matters gud.”(IDI-04)

(I talk to her directly, or sometimes, if our principal is not present, I will chat with her. Our principal is very approachable, especially when it is about school-related matters.)

It is also the priority of language teachers to speak with the principal or their immediate head about any school-related matters they may have with the school as soon as possible. This tailored approach guarantees timely and efficient handling of critical circumstances. Language teachers believe that in-person conversations are very important, especially when it comes to pressing issues that need to be resolved right away. This tactic promotes open conversation and a more thorough comprehension of the circumstances. In the end, direct communication language teachers make sure that big issues are resolved in the classroom. As Participant 7 stated,

(Kung kanang ASAP gyud sya pwede ragyud actually pwede ragyud mo diritso sa among head.”(IDI-07)

(If it is ASAP or urgent, it is very possible to approach our head directly.)

On top of that, language teachers highly value direct communication, especially when it pertains to important school-related matters, particularly those concerning students' statuses. They prioritize face-to-face discussions to ensure that critical issues are effectively addressed. This personal approach allows for immediate clarification and resolution of concerns, ensuring that students' needs are met promptly. By engaging in direct communication, language teachers demonstrate their commitment to student welfare and academic success. Ultimately, this hands-on approach fosters a supportive and proactive school environment. As participant 9 said,

“Kung importante jud sya nga mga school related matters like about the grade or something ana nga importante jud kaayu ng matters. I communicate it personally to our school head/school head.”(IDI-09)

(If it is a very important school-related matter, such as grades or other significant issues, I personally communicate it to our school head.)

Communicating with Authority Figure. This is the second code for the first probed issue. The language teachers expressed that they intended to discuss their worries with the administration of the school. They believe that direct communication with those in positions of authority is crucial when it comes to major issues or concerns. This process makes sure that important concerns are successfully and quickly brought to the attention of the appropriate people. To ensure that their instructions are received and understood, language teachers keep in touch with administrators, head teachers, and other authorities. This direct contact method improves the school community's ability to solve problems by giving it the flexibility to move swiftly when needed.

In connection to that, language teachers communicate with their school head or principal especially if it is about their job as a teacher. Effective communication between teachers and authority figures is crucial for addressing job-related concerns and aligning them with school policies. Teachers should engage in direct discussions with school leadership to address issues promptly and collaboratively, fostering a positive work environment and contributing to the overall success of the educational institution. As Participant 3 stated,

“Communication is mao gyud nay pinaka importante labi na sa naa mi mga panginahanglanon nga mga trabahoon. Kinahanglan gyud kanunay nga magcommunicate sa atiang ahhh principal or kinsa man or kinsa man ang nakataas sa atoa.” (IDI-03)

(Communication is very important especially when it involves our job-related needs. It is essential to communicate with our principal or whoever is above us.)

Participant 5 further emphasized that he will always speak with his principal in a courteous manner. He stressed the importance of acting honorably and professionally in all relationships. Relationships at work are enhanced by this tactic, which maintains positive and open channels of communication. By using a polite tone, Participant 5 intends to encourage collaboration and respect for one another in the classroom. Ultimately, he believes that courteous communication is necessary for effective teamwork and achieving common goals. He stated,

“I will talk to our school head whatever it is to clarify things. If I needed something from my school head I will just go to her office and then “maam I have something to tell you”. Just open to your school head.” (IDI-05)

(I will talk to our school head whatever it is to clarify things. If I needed something from my school head I would just go to her office and then “Ma'am I have something to tell you”. Just open to your school head)

Language teachers stated that they receive regular invitations to the office to discuss a variety of matters with the principal or their direct supervisors. Important school-related issues are discussed promptly and openly thanks to this process. The fact that you were called into the office implies how urgent or significant the matter is. Additionally, it enables the creation of a focused, calm environment that is perfect for productive dialogue. Ultimately, this tactic improves decision-making and hones the problem-solving skills of the school administration. As Participant 5 further stated,

“...Murag importante jud and personal, mag meet jud mo so mao nang importante nga magmeet in person or kung dili man in person para maistoryahan ang mga unsay concerns or mga I relay nga informations. (IDI-01)

(...“It’s essential and personal, you need to meet. That’s why it’s important to meet in person, or if not in person, so that concerns can be discussed or information can be relayed.”.)

In addition, instructors go to their master teachers for advice, particularly on concerns or issues pertaining to the institution. These master instructors are in a position of power, knowledge, and authority among the teaching team. Their experience and skill make them excellent resources to cope with a variety of education-related challenges. They are often consulted by teachers when they need guidance and support due of their leadership qualities and willingness to help out colleagues. In the end, the advice of more experienced teachers aids in the teaching community’s ability to come to thoughtful decisions. As participant 7 stated,

“Kung immediate ang concern nga kuan I would go I would ask the kuan first or we communicate to our MT sa senior high school. So sa MT bago sa among school head.” (IDI-07.)

(If the concern is immediate, I would first approach our master teacher in senior high school, then the school head)

In general, language teachers place a higher priority on social connections than academic ones, especially when they are talking with the head of the institution or the administration. They greatly value the advice and guidance that they get from their immediate superiors. This strategy makes sure that significant problems are handled within the school community in a timely and efficient manner. Language teachers who value the counsel and judgment of their immediate supervisors foster a collaborative and encouraging work atmosphere. In the end, prioritizing interpersonal communication benefits everyone since it fosters closer bonds and better understanding. As Participant 8 stated,

“Every time that there are, there are school-related matters regarding the concerns here in the school. The very first thing I done is I approach her, I approach gyud nako sya. Then discuss everything about the situation.” (IDI-08)

(Every time there are school-related matters or concerns, my immediate action is to approach her, I really approach her. Then, I discuss everything about the situation with her.)

Employing Openness and Acceptance in Communication. In the context of organizational communication language teachers constantly acknowledge the value of many viewpoints and respect those of others. They think recommendations have to be taken into consideration, especially if they help the company accomplish its objectives. In this collaborative setting, each team member will feel respected and heard because of the inclusive approach. Language teachers make sure that decisions are well-informed and represent the opinions of the group by promoting idea-sharing. In the end, the school community is strengthened and becomes more capable of accomplishing its goals as a result of this dedication to accepting diversity.

Communicating Openly and Accepting Ideas. This is the first code for the second probed issue. Language instructors value open communication among themselves and foster an environment where differing viewpoints are respected and embraced. The inclusive approach in language teaching involves an analytical process that considers opposing viewpoints to reach an agreement. This approach fosters creativity, ownership, and dedication among members. By fostering a cooperative, polite atmosphere, language teachers can work towards shared objectives. By being receptive to different viewpoints, teachers can create a productive and successful learning environment.

Similarly, Participant 1 stated that understanding the teaching community is crucial for fostering an environment where ideas are openly shared, leading to collective growth and improvement. Teachers are encouraged to express their ideas, considering their perspectives and contributing to the institution’s well-being. This inclusive approach ensures decisions are made with stakeholders’ best interests in mind, fostering a culture of collaboration and innovation that ultimately leads to effective strategies benefiting the entire teaching community. She stated,

“Kung naa mi meetings, kami tanan gina tagaan jud mi og opportunity nga moistorya. Unsa imong mga suggestions, unsa imong comments and everything.” (IDI-01)

“If ever katanggap tanggap ang opinion. Katanggap tanggap unya mas kanang ginaingon is good for everyone so dawaton.” (IDI-01)

(If we have meetings, all of us are given the chance an opportunity to speak. If what will be our suggestions, comments, and everything)

(If ever opinions are acceptable. Acceptable and what so called for the good of everyone, accept it)

Participant 1 also added that ultimately knowing and communicating successfully require having intimate talks. Participation from all sides in the discussions encourages a more thorough exchange of concepts and points of view. Each member adds unique insights that enrich the conversation. To fully understand the issue, all parties concerned can actively participate. This comprehensive approach cultivates connections and increases trust, which ultimately increases the probability of reaching a win-win outcome. She stated,

“... murag importante jud and personal, mag meet jud mo so mao nang importante nga magmeet in person or kung dili man in person para maistoryahan ang mga unsay concerns or mga I relay nga information.” (IDI-01)

(it indeed appears crucial to communicate personally; meeting in person is vital so that any concerns and information can be discussed thoroughly)

In addition, the language teaching community welcomes and values all voices, regardless of their positions, fostering an inclusive environment that encourages creativity and innovation. This egalitarian approach promotes a culture of collaboration and mutual respect, ensuring decisions are made based on the merit of ideas rather than hierarchical status. The embracing of ideas from all members enriches the teaching process and contributes to the overall success of the institution. As Participant 2 stated,

“If ever I find na theres suggestions have some sense of course dawaton jud na sya. Regardless, kung taas kag position or dili.” (IDI-02)

(If I find that a suggestion makes sense, of course, I will accept it, regardless of your position.)

Moreover, valuing ideas based on their potential contribution to common goals fosters a collaborative mindset. This approach prioritizes decisions with the group's overarching objectives in mind, encouraging individuals to propose solutions that benefit the entire team. This collaborative mindset fosters unity and cooperation among team members, ultimately promoting a more cohesive and effective working environment. Thus, valuing ideas based on their potential impact on common goals is crucial for achieving shared objectives. As Participant 2 added,

“...there are also instances nga dili pod dawaton no, ana. Ug naay mga instances nga ingon ana, pero in may part kung akoy naay kung sa akoa mag suggest ginadawat jud nako sya nya tan-awon lang pd jud kung ang probable end result niya is kanang towards the positive side jud pd ba.” (IDI-02)

(...there are instances where suggestions may not be accepted, but on my part, if there is a suggestion, I will consider accepting it, ensuring that its probable end result is positive)

Furthermore, organizations that value diverse ideas are more likely to find innovative solutions. By actively listening to these ideas, organizations foster a culture of collaboration and mutual respect. This approach not only benefits the organization but also leads to the discovery of new opportunities and approaches to challenges. By embracing a culture of listening, organizations can adapt to change more effectively and achieve their goals more efficiently. As Participant 3 stated,

“Paminawn jud nato sya kung, kung in terms pud na ang iyang idea is makaayu sa tanan so we need to accept the information nga tama rapud.” (IDI-03)

(We really need to listen to him/her, especially if his/her ideas are for the betterment of everybody. Therefore, we need to accept the information which is correct.)

Participant 3 also added that language teachers play a crucial role in achieving organizational goals by accepting diverse ideas. By valuing and accepting these ideas, they foster creativity and innovation within the teaching community. This inclusive approach ensures the best solutions are identified and implemented, advancing the organization's mission. By accepting ideas that align with organizational goals, language teachers facilitate growth and progress within the institution, ultimately contributing to the overall success of the organization. She stated,

“Accept kung unsa may mga ideas, unsa manay ilang unsa man ang mga kinahanglanon nga maachieve is we need to accept and to share.” (IDI-03.)

(Accepting different ideas, whatever the need to be achieved, is essential. We need to accept and share them)

Likewise, the organizational goals are achieved in a collaborative environment that honors divergent opinions. Teachers are encouraged to share ideas openly because they understand the significance of their contributions to the group's overall success. The application of group creativity is made easier by language departments' openness, which leads to innovative solutions and the accomplishment of organizational objectives. Prioritizing ideas that advance the organization's goals is essential to encouraging growth and advancement within it. As Participant 7 stated,

“The ideas are coming from the teachers or the members within the organization. Kanang all can contribute kaning achievement of the goals kung unsay ginainvision sa school.” (IDI-07)

(The ideas are coming from the teachers or the members within the organization. Everyone can contribute to the achievement of the goals and to whatever the school envisions)

Furthermore, sharing ideas is crucial in fostering a culture of collaboration and mutual support among teachers. Teachers, as family members, feel valued and empowered to contribute ideas, fostering creativity and innovation. This practice strengthens relationships among teachers, fostering unity and camaraderie. By collectively tackling challenges and working towards common goals, teachers can work towards a positive and inclusive work environment, where everyone's voice is heard and respected. As Participant 10 stated,

“It really big help with us by sharing our ideas and perspective, we work as one and family. so, to better achieve our goals.” (IDI-10)

(Sharing our ideas and perspectives is a significant help to us; it allows us to work as one cohesive family, thus enhancing our ability to achieve our goals.)

Communicating with Respect and Openness. This is the second code for the second probed issue. In order to promote a cooperative and encouraging atmosphere, language teacher stress the need of honesty and respect in their work. These attributes facilitate the open exchange of ideas and points of view while encouraging innovation and problem-solving. Language teachers place a high importance on these communication abilities because they foster an environment where people can cooperate and understand one another. This strategy makes use of the team's creativity and collective knowledge to assist the business in achieving its goals.

In connection to that, It will be simpler for language teachers to adopt excellent teaching strategies and develop in their careers if they are willing to seek assistance from others and work cooperatively. This collaborative approach encourages teachers to develop a culture of growth and support for one another. Teachers can raise the standard of education they give their pupils by exchanging ideas and resources, strengthening the teaching profession. As Participant 5 stated,

“And besides dili mi maulaw mag ask og help kay kuan naman mi kanang dili maulaw mangayug tabang kay close na then ang communication is open. Walay barrier kumbaga bha. So kung naa mi kanang gikinanghanglan nga halimbawa dali rata kaingon nga “ayy, diko kabalo aning excel, magkuan ko ninyu bi tabangi sa ko bi”. Then dali rapd sila mutabang.” (IDI-05.)

(And besides, we are not shy to ask for help because we are close with each other, and communication is open. There are no barriers. So, if we need something, for example, we can easily say, "I don't know how to use Excel, can I ask for a favor? Can you help me with this?" Then, they will help easily)

Likewise, in the workplace, good communication is essential to fostering team trust and cooperation. By fostering a pleasant workplace culture, miscommunications and disputes are decreased. This strategy also increases output and teamwork, which raises employee morale and satisfaction. Consequently, keeping friendly and courteous interactions with coworkers is crucial to fostering an environment where team members can succeed. As stated by participant 6,

“Well of course you are going to communicate your colleagues by of course politely and brief and concisely in the sense that we already knew that our colleagues are already knowledgeable so you have to approach them politely and accordingly.” (IDI-06)

(Of course, when communicating with colleagues, it's important to do so politely, briefly, and concisely. We understand that our colleagues are knowledgeable, so it's essential to approach them politely and accordingly.)

In addition, language teachers treat their supervisors with the utmost respect and professionalism when expressing their thoughts. They understand the importance of maintaining friendly and constructive working relationships with their superiors. This tactic upholds the integrity of the teaching profession and fosters a positive work environment in the classroom. By fusing professionalism and respect, teachers uphold the standards of their profession and effectively express their ideas to superiors. As participant 6 added,

“... you have to ammm start with ahhh greetings “hi maam, can I have something to discuss about on this matter. If it is ok for you ma'am that ahhh I am going to ask you about this matter?” of course will always be polite, talking our superior.” (IDI-06.)

(...you have to start with greetings “Hi ma'am, can I have something to discuss on this matter. If it is ok for you ma'am that I am going to ask you about this matter?” of course will always be polite, talking our superior.)

Likewise, educators in the teaching community take an unbiased stance and appreciate and acknowledge the opinions of one another. This promotes cooperation and respect for one another, which in turn creates an atmosphere that is conducive to invention and creativity. Instructors are aware that every team member contributes something different to the table that helps the group succeed and develop. Better teamwork and communication are fostered in an atmosphere of openness and respect, which is advantageous to both teachers and students. As participant 6 stated,

“If there will be a suggestions of course you have to listen, and respect when there are suggestions because it was raised because they know that it would be for the help for everyone.” (IDI-06.)

(If there are suggestions, of course, you have to listen and respect them because they are raised with the intention of helping everyone.)

In addition, language teachers value open communication in their language teaching community, fostering collaboration and innovation. They believe that "two heads are better than one" and pool their collective knowledge to achieve organizational goals. This

approach fosters diverse perspectives, allowing for problem-solving and problem-solving. Teachers create a supportive environment where every voice is heard and valued, enabling them to overcome challenges and drive progress within the organization. As Participant 7 stated,

“Ang importante pud ani is that kuan ahhh the acceptance of the different perspective sa members within the organization. Meaning to say kung accepted ang ideas nila mas better compared sya sa isa lang ang mudala o isa lang nga idea ang sundon sa tanan. Kasi it will help grow the organization by looking from the different perspectives in which kato nga different perspective sya naka point out pud sya sa different concerns within the school.” (IDI-07.)

(The important thing here is the acceptance of different perspectives from members within the organization. Meaning to say, if the ideas are acceptable, it is much better compared to only one person having the authority to express ideas and be followed. This approach helps the organization grow by considering various perspectives, which can also highlight different concerns within the school.)

Moreover, effective communication requires active listening since it enables others to comprehend one's obligations and tasks. By fostering rapport, trust, and collaboration, this technique reduces misunderstandings and increases output. People may effectively complete tasks and fulfill their responsibilities by making listening a priority, which also makes sure that everyone feels heard and valued. Building trust among the team encourages more efficient practices and a spirit of unity. As Participant 3 stated,

“First is communication jud no maminaw ka kung unsa man ang iyahang ahhh ginaingon para maaccomplish nato ang atong mga task and responsibility.” (IDI-03.)

(In communication, the first step is to listen to what others say in order to accomplish our tasks and responsibilities.)

Furthermore, language teachers should adopt an open-minded approach to foster inclusivity, innovation, and growth in their teaching. This approach encourages diverse perspectives and encourages continuous learning and professional development. It encourages collaboration among colleagues, fostering strong bonds and effective teamwork. By prioritizing open-mindedness, language educators can create environments where creativity, innovation, and collective aspirations are transformed into tangible achievements, empowering team members and contributing to the institution's success. As Participant 10 stated,

“Siguro maging open-minded and engage in a purposeful dialogue are my way to accept information and suggestions.” (IDI-10.)

(Being open-minded and engaging in purposeful dialogue are my ways of accepting information and suggestions.)

Utilizing Effective Communication Strategies. in order to maintain clear and consistent communication in interpersonal relationships, language teachers are essential. To promote smooth interactions, they use techniques including accurate articulation, nonverbal clues, and attentive listening. These tactics reduce misunderstandings between teachers and coworkers and provide a peaceful, conducive learning atmosphere. Teachers are inspired to improve their communication skills when these strategies are consistently used because they provide a positive example for them. Ultimately, these techniques improve teacher collaboration and comprehension while improving the teaching and learning process.

Practicing Effective Communication. This is the first code for the third probed issue. Effective communication is crucial for language teachers to foster a collaborative environment and improve understanding among their students. By practicing communication skills like active listening and clear articulation, teachers can enhance their comprehension of each other's perspectives, facilitating smoother collaboration in lesson planning and curriculum development. By prioritizing communication, teachers serve as role models for their students, reinforcing the importance of clarity and coherence in all communication.

Similarly, Participant 6 stated that language teachers often receive detailed explanations from their superiors to ensure understanding and support their professional development. These explanations clarify objectives, expectations, and steps, instilling confidence and empowering them to execute tasks effectively. Clear communication fosters a collaborative and productive relationship between leadership and educators, ensuring language teachers feel valued and respected. This framework for effective collaboration and organizational goals is established. As he stated,

“If you fulfill something, you are able to fulfill your task. But of course, if somehow if there is something lacking of course she reminds us that “this will be the things you will do next time” something like that. So, in ammm professional manner.” (IDI-06.)

(If you fulfill something, you are able to fulfill your task. But of course, if there is somehow something lacking, she reminds us that 'these will be the things you will do next time,' something like that. So in professional manner)

In addition, a structured process is employed by language teachers to ensure professionalism and efficient communication with colleagues. This process involves checking availability and time, fostering a supportive and cooperative culture within the teaching community. By consulting with colleagues, teachers can gather insights and advice on how to approach interactions with their immediate heads, demonstrating respect for the organizational structure. As Participant 10 stated,

“I communicate my school related matters to my principal by asking my colleagues. Kung naa ba among principal sa office then after ana I- present nako sa iyaha kung unsa akong mga plano regarding sa activities og unsa pa ang maayu pa ug unsa pa ang maayung buhaton para sa mga activities.” (IDI-10)

(I communicate my school-related matters to my principal by first checking with my colleagues. If our principal is present in the office, I then proceed to present my plans regarding activities and discuss the appropriate course of action for these activities.

Furthermore, effective communication is crucial for language teachers to maintain professionalism and build strong relationships with their colleagues. It fosters transparency, empathy, and active listening, allowing teachers to articulate their thoughts, express their needs, and advocate for their students and the profession. This culture of mutual respect and support allows language teachers to work collaboratively with colleagues, administrators, and other stakeholders, enhancing their effectiveness and enriching the teaching and learning experience. As participant 9 stated,

“... it has a huge impact no dili lang sa ako personally,so sa tibuuik namo diri sa among office or sa school.” (IDI-09)

“... we communicate it sa meetings sa office saamong principal.” (IDI-09)

(... it has a huge impact not just on me personally, but also on all of us here in our office or school.)

(... we communicate it in meetings in the office of our principal.)

Utilizing Group Chats. This is the second code for the third probed issue. Group chat has become the primary medium for teachers, facilitating quick information dissemination, real-time updates, and task coordination. This technology promotes inclusivity, transparency, and collaboration among teachers. Its searchable archives and message history features facilitate continuity and coherence in communication, enabling teachers to transcend geographical barriers, optimize workflow efficiency, and enhance their professional communication practices.

Similarly, Participant 2 stated that technology is revolutionizing language teachers' communication processes, enhancing connectivity, resource sharing, and activity coordination. Teachers use group chats for information dissemination, while separate chats are created for urgent issues, fostering a collaborative teaching community and facilitating quick decision-making and problem-solving. She stated,

“Naa jud mi ana nga gc nya nakalahi jud na sya. Naay gc for issuances or pang mema lang jud, naay gc for documentation lang jud ang school.” (IDI-02.)

(We really have our own GC's. There is a GC for issuances for chika-chika, and there is also a GC for documentation purposes of our school only.)

In addition, group chats are widely utilized by language teachers as a means of communication. They use their respective group chats to communicate with each other. Language teachers have stated that their school head also utilizes these group chats to provide direction regarding activities both inside and outside the school premises. As Participant 4 stated,

“We have school gc in which didto mi naga communicates usahay or mostly kay mag pa meeting.” (IDI-04)

“... iyaha meng gina pahibalo ahead of time about sa mga events or if ever naay mga himuonon through group gc or meeting. Kay in that way, dili me mag ba buang if agad agad kay dili lalim ang preparation every event or unsa diba.” (IDI-04)

(We have a school GC in which we sometimes communicate through there or mostly we will hold meetings.)

(... We are informed ahead of time about the events or if there are tasks that we need to do through GC or meetings. In that way, we will not be shocked because it is not easy to prepare for an event.)

Moreover, language teachers, like other educators, often opt for Messenger for less serious matters. It's a convenient way for them to communicate without the formality of other platforms. This informal approach helps streamline communication among colleagues. As Participant 9 stated,

“kung simple lang nga matter if it concerns lang sa mga bata is I communicate is sa gc lang.” (IDI-09)

(If it's a simple matter that concerns only students, I communicate through our group chat only.)

Utilization of Formal Communication Channels. Immediate heads use memos as official documents to communicate with teachers, ensuring clarity, consistency, and accountability. These documents outline directives, updates, and important information, serving as a record of instructions and decisions made within the educational institution. This approach underscores professionalism and organizational structure within the educational environment, promoting transparency and accountability within the administrative hierarchy.

Utilizing Memoranda. This is the first code for fourth probed issue. Teachers play a crucial role in the effective communication and coordination of school activities. The immediate head uses memos as formal channels to convey important information, such as event schedules, policies, and guidelines. This ensures consistent and structured communication, streamlines coordination, and ensures everyone is informed and aligned. Memos also provide a documented record for clarification or accountability purposes, underscoring professionalism and organizational discipline within the school environment. Overall, memos play a crucial role in facilitating effective communication and coordination.

Similarly, participant 7 stated that teachers are instructed by their immediate head through memos, which serve as formal directives outlining tasks, policies, and procedures. This ensures clear and consistent communication, maintains organizational structure, and maintains accountability within the school hierarchy. Memos provide a documented record of instructions, ensuring all teachers receive the necessary information for effective duties. He state that,

“Naami school memo from time-to-time labi na ug mga advisory, activities, task and conferences always gyud naka memo. So coming from our school head down to kuan, bali ang arrangement is naay memo crafted by our head tapos channeled through our MT’s and then muabot gyud sa amoa.” (IDI-07)

(We have school memo from time to time specially if there are advisory, activities, task and conferences it always through memo.so, coming from our school head down to us, the arrangement is if there is a memo crafted by our school head then channeled through our MT’s and then to us.)

In addition, language teachers expresses that if the matter is really important, they communicated by their immediate head through memorandum. As Participant 9 stated,

“Kung importante na gyud naay mga Kmemo. Like kung kailangan jud istoryahan na sa tanang mga teachers kana jud. Kanang kung important jud sya kaayu nga matter for example naay bag-o nga issue ang deped, naa jud nay memo ang principal nga ipadla sa amoa for to communicate that information.” (IDI-09)

(If it is important, it is through a memo. Like if it needs to be discussed by all of the teachers. If it is a very important matter for example there is a new issue from DEPED, we do have a memo from our principal which delivered to us to communicate that information.)

Recognizing and Mitigating of Communication Challenges. Communication issues in organizations can lead to misunderstandings and hinder productivity, collaboration, and overall cohesion. These issues can be caused by unclear instructions, differing interpretations, or inadequate communication channels. Addressing these challenges requires a proactive approach, including clarifying expectations, fostering open dialogue, and using multiple channels. Prioritizing effective communication strategies can promote a harmonious and efficient working environment.

Recognizing the Impact of Miscommunication. This is the first code for the fifth probed issue Miscommunication is a significant issue in any organization, causing confusion, frustration, and decreased productivity. It can also lead to errors, misunderstandings, missed opportunities, and damage relationships. To prevent this, organizations can improve communication channels, provide training, and foster a culture of transparency. This understanding enhances efficiency, collaboration, and overall performance by prioritizing clear communication.

Similarly, Participant 2 stated that misunderstandings among teachers are common, requiring immediate attention to maintain harmony within the school environment. Addressing these issues promptly helps foster positive relationships and effective collaboration among staff members. By resolving misunderstandings swiftly, schools can create a conducive atmosphere for teaching and learning. She stated,

“It helps a lot jud sya, kay kung walay ingon ana naa juy mga miscommunication no. so importante gyud kaayu sya, makatabang sya in a way that para each of the teachers here nga in school naa silay voice ba.” (IDI-02)

(It helps a lot, because if there is nothing like that there will be a miscommunication. So, it is really important, it can help in a way that each of the teachers here in our school will have a voice.)

In addition, language teachers expressed that through communication they will be notified about the happening inside and outside the school premises. Through communication they will be instructed of the things which they need to accomplish. As Partipant 3 stated,

“kung wala moy communication dili ninyu masabtan kung unsa gyud ang inyung mga importanteng information nga dapat gyud nga mahibal-an.” (IDI-03)

(If there are no communication you won’t understand of what is the important information which you need to know.)

Moreover, Participant 2 also added that as a teacher they sometimes forgot to read what is written in the memo. Therefor they often misunderstood the things that their immediate head and colleagues want convey into them. She stated,

“...di nata mubasag memo. Mao nang naa diha nang misunderstanding unsahay.” (IDI-02)

(... I won’t read the memo. That is where the misunderstanding start, sometimes.)

Seeking Improvement Through Communication. This is the second code for the fifth probed issue. Effective communication is crucial for an organization's growth and success. It involves open dialogue, feedback, and change implementation. This fosters an environment for open discussion, identifying areas for improvement and addressing concerns. Regular communication channels like meetings, feedback sessions, and surveys foster collaboration and continuous improvement. Prioritizing communication allows organizations to adapt to challenges, enhance performance, and achieve goals effectively.

Efficiency In Managing and Leveraging Information.	<p>indicators of healthy communication. Acknowledging the opinions of others. Being open-minded to maintain health communication. Considering communication as healthy due to consistency.</p> <p>Importance of cooperating with one another. Communicating with the people involved if an issue arises.</p> <p>Usefulness of communication in an organization. Importance of staying updated, especially regarding who needs to be informed about concerns, requiring consistent informing.</p> <p>Not being properly informed at times can lead to added pressure when tasked with reports, underscoring the importance of staying updated within the teaching community.</p> <p>Better to be personally informed or to have a meeting to ensure proper communication.</p> <p>Conflicts may arise due to misunderstandings stemming from inadequate communication.</p> <p>Importance of reading and listening carefully to avoid miscommunication.</p> <p>Importance of protocol to conduct an information drive as the first step when implementing a program, ensuring that everyone involved is well-informed.</p> <p>Utilizing group chats for regular communications. Communicating to easily get the job done.</p> <p>Using appropriate language when communicating with students or colleagues.</p> <p>Importance of communication to be aware of the task.</p>	<p>Acceptance</p> <p>Fostering Collaborative Communication Practices</p> <p>Importance of Staying Informed</p> <p>Significance of Utilizing Effective Communication Channels</p>	Effective Information Management is Essential in Organization	Information Theory
Quality Of Relationships Formed and Commitment to Communication Improvement	<p>Openness and transparency are fundamental to effective communication, as exemplified by the practices within the school where they maintain an open environment for everyone involved.</p> <p>Having good communication allows a harmonious organization.</p> <p>Principal is proactive when it comes to disseminating information and preparing the agenda.</p> <p>Being open in sharing and communicating.</p> <p>Doing something to get the school head's attention for commendation or recommendation.</p> <p>Communicating with the personnel to facilitate improvement.</p> <p>Attending seminars related to your course.</p> <p>Importance of respecting others in communicating to fill the gaps between.</p>	<p>Building Harmonious Relationships through Communication</p> <p>Continuous Improvement through Communication</p>	Nurturing Relationship and Continuous Improvement is Possible with Effective Communication	Social Penetration Theory

Embracing Open Communication and Innovation is Important in Organization. The insights of the language teachers in accordance to their organizational communication are being elaborated based from the similar responses given by the participants. Based from the information given by the participants, it is claimed that having an open and innovation of communication is important withing the organization. In order to effectively exchange thoughts and ideas withing colleagues and immediate heads.

Impact of Effective Communication Practices. This is the first code for the first probed issue. Participants suggested that having an effective communication within an organization help to avoid misunderstandings and miscommunication. It will promote a harmonious environment and collaboration withing the language teacher.

Similarly, language teachers indicate that effective communication will enable them to avoid any reason for them to overthink the happenings within and even outside the school premises. This will also enable them to focus on their job as a language teacher and it will avoid stress. As Participant 9 stated,

“Organizational communication affect my job kay of course for you as teacher kanag daghan nakag gina huna-huna nga lessons, gina huna-huna pa nimo ang mga bata and of course kung naam oy kanang communication in your organization dili naka maka overthink nga hala naa bakaha toy gimeetingan nga something or naa ba toy something nga wala naingon si maam sa akoo. Of course kung naa moy good organizational communication kanang of course informed ka pirmente. So dili naka maka overthink kung naa ba kay wala nahibal-an.” (IDI-09.)

(Organizational communication affects my job. As a teacher, I have a lot of lessons to plan and consider, in addition to thinking about my students. If there is effective communication within my organization, I won't overthink things or worry about information that my superiors may not have shared with me. With good organizational communication, I am always informed, which prevents me from overthinking about unknown factors.)

Moreover, Language teachers often face misunderstandings, which can negatively impact their work. To address these, they initiate conversations with those who misunderstand their actions or words. This proactive approach fosters effective communication, resolves conflicts, and promotes mutual understanding, ensuring a harmonious and productive working environment. As Participant 4 stated,

“It will affect myself as a language teacher kay I will kanang I con not concentrate if I have ... I have an enemy here. Ako man gud ang tao kung naay naka, mahiubos sa akua diko mahimutang.” (IDI-04)

(It will affect me as a language teacher because I cannot concentrate if there is discord among my colleagues. Personally, I find it difficult to focus if someone is disappointed in me.)

Furthermore, language teachers take proactive steps to resolve conflicts with colleagues, demonstrating a commitment to maintaining a harmonious working environment. They prioritize open communication and mutual understanding, promoting collaboration and cooperation among colleagues, thereby fostering a conducive atmosphere for teaching and learning. As Participant 2 stated,

“Then kung naa man galing sa misunderstanding magkig istorya jud ka dapat you need to talk with that person. Di nimo ipalabi ang pride. Whoever or regardless kung kinsa ang sad an.” (IDI-02)

(Then, if there are misunderstandings, I will talk to that person. Don't let your pride get in the way, regardless of who may have been at fault.)

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(Then, if there are misunderstandings, I will talk to that person. Don't let your pride get in the way, regardless of who may have been at fault)

Embracing Openness and Collaboration. This is the second code for the first probed issue. Participants elaborated on the importance of promoting openness in communication among themselves as language teachers. They expressed that fostering such openness would cultivate camaraderie and create a harmonious working environment. With regard to their communication, they emphasized the need to avoid misunderstandings with each other.

Similarly, participants indicated a willingness to communicate and discuss with their colleagues the necessary elements for fostering good relationships. Necessary elements for fostering good relationships, recognizing that open dialogue is essential. They expressed a desire to cultivate collaboration to better focus on their roles as teachers. As Participant 2 stated,

“... willing lang jud ka to compromise and willing lang pud ka to come with a dialogue with whoever the person nga involve pud ana. Ingon ana lang jud sya willingness to compromise, willingness to forgive kung naa man lang gani wa nagkasinabot sa kanang mga panghitabo” (IDI-02)

(...willing to compromise and willing to come up with a dialogue with whoever the person involved. Just like that, willingness to compromise, willingness to forgive if there are misunderstood happenings.)

Moreover, Participants indicated that as language teachers, they deeply respected each other. They valued each other's ideas and were open to accepting suggestions from their peers. They viewed themselves not as competitors but as a family, sharing the same career path in life. They believed that this sense of camaraderie would aid in their professional development as teachers. As Participant 9 stated,

“We respect those other teachers man pud nga halimbawa naa silay concern nya wala mo nagka sinabtanay. Of course I respect other teachers and communicate well to them kay sila man imon mga katrabaho, sila man imong kauban pirmente. So kailangan jud ninyu og kanang peace sa inyung workplace.” (IDI-09.)

(We also respect other teachers, for example, if they have concerns and we haven't understood each other. Of course, I respect other teachers and communicate well with them because they are your colleagues, they are always your companions. So, you really need to have that peace in your workplace.)

Furthermore, communication enables language teachers to freely share their ideas within the organization. The participants stated that they could share their suggestions and have the opportunity to discuss and weigh them to determine the best course of action. As Participant 1 stated,

“Kay mao gni to sya if ammm naa kay suggestions you can share those ideas and naa paman joy mas maayu ana mao ganing magsabot sabot para kung asa ang mas maayu.” (IDI-01)

(Because that's how it is, if you have suggestions, you can share those ideas, and there might be even better ones, so it's better to discuss and understand each other to determine what's best.)

Appreciating Openness and Acceptance. This is the third code for the first probed issue. Language teachers emphasize the importance of open communication within the organization, facilitating the exchange of ideas and suggestions. Furthermore, they underscore the significance of accepting someone's suggestions, which fosters collaboration and innovation among colleagues.

Similarly, language teachers emphasize the importance of effective communication within their organization, where all members can share their ideas and be heard by the majority, as long as it contributes to the improvement of their school. This inclusive approach fosters a sense of ownership and collaboration among the staff. As Participant 6 stated,

“For us to be able to develop our communications we have to ammm welcome any suggestions. You have appreciate whatever suggestions they have as long as you understand each other.” (IDI-06.)

(For us to develop our communication, we have to welcome any suggestions. You have to appreciate whatever suggestions they have as long as you understand each other.)

Moreover, A healthy organization often involves disagreements and misunderstandings among colleagues, which can lead to constructive criticism and arguments. Language teachers stress that this is a normal part of organizational dynamics. They acknowledge that such interactions occur within their own professional circles. As Participant 6 also added,

“Because within an organization or in an organization we can not really avoid that there are some kind of argumentations, suggestions and even criticisms of something like that and that is an indications of healthy. Why, because everyone is thinking.’ (IDI-06)

(Because within an organization, we cannot really avoid having some form of arguments, suggestions, and even criticisms, and that is an indication of healthiness. Why? Because everyone is thinking.)

Furthermore, Language teachers point out that within their school community, their voices are valued and their ideas are heard, not only by their colleagues but also by their immediate superiors, especially when there are meetings of the organization. They emphasize that their immediate heads consistently keep them informed in advance about school-related matters. As Participant 4 stated,

“Well sa amoa diria, i can say nga okay man. Gina hear man nila ang sides sa uban namo teacher's specially sa meeting namo. Healthy man among communication process here in our school. sa amoa pung school head, maayo man iyang pag dala para sa akong ge ingon gaina nga iya ming gipa pahibalo ahead of time sa mga event and memo's unsahay gina chat sad sa me niya ahead of time.” (IDI-04)

(In our opinion, I can say that it's good. They really listen to the perspectives of our fellow teachers, especially during our meetings. Our communication process here in our school is healthy. As for our school head, he handles things well. Like what I mentioned earlier, he informs us ahead of time about events and memos. Sometimes, he even chats with us ahead of time.)

Fostering Collaborative Communication Practices. This is the fourth code for the first probed issue. Language teachers emphasize the presence of a collaborative communication process within their organization. They often seek assistance from one another in various situations, confident that the organizational structure enables them to address any challenges they encounter. They trust in the efficiency of the support and assistance provided by their colleagues.

Similarly, language teachers truly recognize the significant role of organizational communication in addressing all school-related matters. It facilitates their professional growth by fostering open suggestions from fellow teachers and beyond. They emphasize the profound impact of organizational communication on their development as members of the language teachers' organization. As Participant 3 stated,

“... communication in an organization daku kaayu syag matabang.” (IDI-03)

(Communication within an organization is immensely helpful.)

In addition, language teachers prioritize maintaining positive relationships with their colleagues. They value truth over falsehoods and actively avoid misunderstandings to foster strong connections among themselves. They approach and talk for each other. As Participant 8 stated,

“Dili nako tubayan ang mga istorya nga kanang makapadaut sa relasyon sa matag usa. Makiangayun ramn pud mi tanan diri. Approachable rman pd mi tanan, maminaw if unsay gusto iopen sa isa mga concerns.” (IDI-08)

(I don't entertain stories that could damage relationships among us. We all readily engage here. We're all approachable and willing to listen to each other's concerns.)

Effective Information Management is Essential in Organization. Language teachers express the importance of keeping each other

informed about school events to ensure smooth coordination and effective collaboration. While they occasionally miss updates, they make an effort to seek information from others. They believe that staying updated helps prevent conflicts related to activities, meetings, and other important matters both within and outside the school.

Importance of Staying Informed. This is the first code for the second probed issue. Language teachers emphasize the importance of being kept updated on events within their organization and school community. Despite occasional misinformation, they prioritize seeking accurate information over engaging in conflicts with their colleagues. This approach reflects their vision of what an organization should be like.

Similarly, participants mentioned that if they, as teachers, are not updated by their colleagues or immediate superiors, they take the initiative to seek the information they missed. However, language teachers indicate that this rarely occurs in their organization because they are usually informed ahead of time about upcoming events or occurrences. As Participant 1 stated,

“Murag naay mga instances nga wala ka nainform og tarong unya naa kay report nga buhaton so maiwit ka. So mas maayu nga para maging updated sa imohang, sa pagkuan. Unsay mga nahitabo sa imong, between sa community. (IDI-01)

(It seems that there are instances when you're not properly informed, then you're suddenly assigned a task, catching you off guard. So it's better to stay updated, to be aware. What's been happening to you, within the community)

In addition, Language teachers acknowledge that occasional arguments arise within their organization due to miscommunications, an inevitability they confront. They address such challenges by initiating dialogues with the involved parties to foster resolution and understanding, thereby promoting a harmonious work environment. As Participant 1 added,

“Mag away – away na noon. Ayy, murag misuderstnadings lang kay murag wala nainform og tarong.” (IDI-01)

(It's already turning into a quarrel. it seems like just misunderstandings because it seems like we weren't properly informed.)

Significance of Utilizing Effective Communication Channels. This is the second code for the second probed issue. Participants indicate that as members of an organization, especially as language teachers, it is crucial to utilize effective communication practices. This ensures that all members can express their ideas and stay updated about school happenings, such as the implementation of new policies. Through effective communication, teachers are informed about the changes occurring within their school.

Similarly, Language teachers elaborate that whenever there are updates from the DepEd, there should be a communication drive to ensure that all language teachers are informed. It's important for them to be updated by their colleagues and immediate supervisors about any changes in the school premises. It is about following the protocols. As Participant 2 stated,

“Diri jud sa DEPED proctocol jud nga if ever your going to implement a program. First step, is that magkuan jud ka mag, naa jud kay information drive ba.” (IDI-02)

(Here in DepEd, it's really a protocol that if you're going to implement a program, the first step is to conduct an information drive.)

In addition, Language teachers emphasize the importance of communication among their colleagues to stay informed about assigned tasks. They rely on each other's assistance, particularly for school-related matters, fostering a collaborative and supportive environment, enhancing efficiency and ensuring that tasks are completed effectively within the school community. As Participant 3 stated,

“Kinahanglanon gyud kaayu ang communications sa bawat isa para kung unsa man lang tong mga trabahoon, task and responsibility dali ra sya mahuman.” (IDI-03)

(Communication among everyone is really essential, so whatever tasks, work, or responsibilities there are, they can be easily accomplished.)

Furthermore, Language teachers emphasize the necessity of being informed in advance about tasks, events, school-related matters, responsibilities, and school happenings. They assert that this keeps them focused on their roles as teachers. As Participant 4 stated,

“It is really important gud kay para ma aware ka sa imong mga buhatonon or kung naay memo ge hatag. Mas okay nang ma ingnan ka daan ahead of time sa mga buhatonon aron dili sad ma apektohan imong pag teach diba.” (IDI-04)

(It's really important because it keeps you aware of your tasks or if there's a memo issued. It's better to be informed in advance about tasks so it won't affect your teaching, right?)

Nurturing Relationships and Continuous Improvement is Possible with Effective Communication. Language teachers emphasize the importance of nurturing good relationships among colleagues to create a harmonious workplace. They stress the continual improvement of organizational communication for the betterment of the school and achieving common goals. Additionally, they underscore the significance of fostering mutual respect, effective collaboration, and teamwork to address challenges and enhance productivity.

Building Harmonious Relationships through Communication. This is the first code for the third probed issue. Participants indicate that building harmonious relationships is the primary aim of language teachers, who assert that effective communication is the key to

achieving this goal. They emphasize the importance of exchanging ideas and sharing important matters to maintain strong relationships with each other.

Similarly, language teachers emphasize that each member of the organization is open and transparent with one another. Through this practice, they are able to build strong bonds and avoid conflicts, which can negatively impact the organization's environment and their roles as teachers. As Participant 10 stated,

“Be open and transparent. That is the key of an effective communication nga maopud ang nahitabopud sa amoang school. Open mi sa matag usag-usa.” (IDI-10)

(Being open and transparent is the key to effective communication, which is also what happens in our school. We're open to each other all the time.)

Moreover, Language teachers emphasize the importance of valuing information within their organization and ensuring that all members are consistently updated. This communication flow extends beyond colleagues to immediate heads, who proactively provide advance notice of tasks and necessary actions for effective execution. Additionally, they promptly communicate meeting schedules to facilitate efficient coordination. As Participant 8 stated,

“Sa principal ammm naga ano d I na sya every time nga naa mi conference naga annanounce na sya ahead of time. Ginapahibalo mi niya dayun nya nakahan-ay na dayun ang iyang mga agenda.” (IDI-08)

(Our principal always informs us ahead of time whenever we have a conference. She announces it in advance and shares her agenda with us promptly.)

Continuous Improvement through Communication. This is the second code for the third probed issue. Language teachers always aim to improve themselves as educators, understanding that perfection is unattainable. This involves seeking assistance from experts, such as their MT and immediate head, for guidance on areas needing improvement. Open communication within the organization facilitates this process.

Similarly, Language teachers actively pursue opportunities to excel in their roles, occasionally seeking recognition from their immediate heads to garner recommendations and feedback, which they can utilize to further improve their teaching practices. As Participant 7 stated,

“Kung ako ing ani ang matter mahimo kung reactive. Meaning to sya kailangan nako mubuhag og isa ka butang in order for it nga kanang makuha pud ang attention ni maam para muhatag pud syag commendation or recommendation if unsay dapat.” (IDI-07)

(If I were in such a situation, I might tend to be reactive. This means I'd feel the need to do something in order to capture Ma'am's attention, hoping to receive commendation or recommendation based on my actions.)

Moreover, Language teachers consistently show respect towards their colleagues and superiors as part of their professionalism. They understand the importance of demonstrating this behavior to be both respectful and respected by others. It's a principle where language teachers receive what they give. As Participant 7 also stated,

“Another one kanang respect,importante gyud na sya. Kay no matter how, wala ka gahatag og respect sa imong superior or ang superior wa naghatag og respect sa mga subordinates wala gyud na sya. Kanang despite naay communication but then again there's something gaps between those communication.” (IDI-07)

(Respect is really important. Because no matter how, if you don't give respect to your superior or the superior doesn't give respect to the subordinates, it's not there. Even if there's communication, there will still be gaps between those communications.)

Data Integration of the Salient Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

The present study on the organizational communication among language teachers of the public school within the division of Davao del Norte carries out a mixed methods approach employing a convergent parallel approach. The third research question of the study involves the corroboration of the findings from the quantitative and qualitative phases.

The table 4 on the salient quantitative and qualitative findings presents the focal points in the first column which contains the aspect or focal points of the study followed by the quantitative and qualitative findings in the second and third column. The findings from the quantitative phase are usually the indicators with the highest mean while the qualitative findings which display the identified responses show confirmation or disconfirmation to the quantitative results. The fourth column is the nature of the data integration and the fifth column contains the axiological implications made based on the data described in the preceding columns.

Utilizing memos as a way of communication. In the quantitative phase, the specific item on informative communication rated as very high is language teachers get most of the information about school news and events via memos/emails/ and chat. This result is connected with the qualitative findings, which is themed as utilizing effective communication strategies. It is then safe to say that the qualitative data converges with the quantitative.

Table 4. *Joint Display of Salient Quantitative and Qualitative Finding*

<i>Aspect Or Focal Point</i>	<i>Quantitative Findings</i>	<i>Qualitative Findings</i>	<i>Nature Of Data Integration</i>	<i>Axiological Implications</i>
Utilizing memos as a way of communication	From Table 1.1 on informative communication item 3 which is about language teachers get most of the information about school news and events via memos/emails/ and chat (M=4.75) which is rated high.	Table 2.1 on utilizing effective communication strategies.	Merging – converging	Immediate head use memos as a form of communication, enabling language teachers to stay informed about school events. It also serves as a formal means of communication among professional educators.
Utilizing Group Chats	From Table 1.1 on informative communication item 3 which is about language teachers get most of the information about school news and events via memos/emails/ and chat (M=4.75) which is rated high	Table 2.1 on theme utilizing effective communication strategies.	Merging – converging	Language teachers utilize group chats to streamline communication with their colleagues. This approach significantly simplifies the exchange of information. They maintain separate group chats—one dedicated solely to issuances and another for discussing important school-related matters.
Striving for Improvement Through Effective Communication.	From Table 1.1 on task-oriented communication item 3 about language teachers who believe the directives that come from the principal is clear and consistent which will lead to performing my tasks efficiently and effectively (M=4.72) which is rated as very high.	Table 2.1 on addressing miscommunication trough collective problem solving.	Merging – converging	Effective communication among language teachers fosters collaboration, idea exchange, and problem-solving, driving continuous improvement within teams and organizations. It enables clarity, alignment, and accountability, propelling collective efforts towards achieving shared goals.
Fostering Open Communication and Embracing Diverse Ideas.	From Table 2 on informative communication item 4 about the language teachers who see the lines of information are “open” to the principal (M=4.64) which is rated as very high.	Table 3 on the theme embracing open communication and innovation is important in organization.	Merging – converging	Language teachers consistently encourage an environment of open dialogue and inclusivity, where diverse perspectives are valued and embraced to enrich the learning experience.
Engaging with Authority Figures Through Effective Communication.	Table 2 on informative communication item 5 about language teachers who believe that my superior provides a sufficient amount of useful information that I understand (m=4.70) which is rated as very high.	Table 3 on the theme establishing open channels and clear lines of communication.	Merging – converging	As language teachers, effectively engaging with authority figures involves clear and respectful communication to foster collaboration and enhance the learning environment.
Embracing Openness and Collaborative Efforts.	From Table 1. 1 on task-oriented communication item 4 about language teachers who consider that my co-teacher and I readily share important information that is critical to our success (M=4.77) which is rated as very high.	Table 4 on under the theme embracing open communication and innovation is important in an organization.	Merging – converging	As a language teacher, embracing openness and collaborative efforts involves actively fostering an environment where ideas are freely exchanged and collective action is taken to enhance student learning outcomes.
The Significance of Effective Communication Practices.	Table 1.1 on task-oriented communication item 2 about language teachers receive the information I need to effectively perform my job, in most of situations (M=4.67) which is rated as very high.	Table 4 on the theme effective information management is essential in organization.	Merging – converging	Language teachers sees effective communication practices have a profound impact on fostering understanding, building trust, and driving positive outcomes in both personal and professional contexts.
Fostering Harmony through Effective Communication.	From Table 1.1 on informative communication item 4 about language teachers who see the lines of information are “open” to the principal (m=4.64) which is rated as very high.	Table 4 on the nurturing relationship and continuous improvement is possible with communication.	Merging – converging	Building harmonious relationships among the teachers through effective communication involves creating an atmosphere of mutual respect, active listening, and clear expression, ultimately fostering understanding and cooperation among individuals.

Utilizing Group Chats. In the quantitative phase, the specific item on informative communication, teachers get most of the information about school news and events via memos/emails/ and chat, is rated as very high. This result is connected to the qualitative findings under the theme utilizing effective communication strategies. Hence, the qualitative data converges quantitative in this aspect.

Striving for Improvement Through Effective Communication. In the quantitative phase, on task-oriented communication about language teachers believe the directives that come from the principal is clear and consistent which will lead to performing my tasks efficiently and effectively, is rated as very high by the respondents. This result is connected with the qualitative findings, which is the addressing miscommunication through collective problem solving. It is then safe to say that the qualitative data converges quantitative.

Fostering Open Communication and Embracing Diverse Ideas. The specific item on informative communication, which rated as very high is language teachers see the lines of information are “open” to the principal. This result is connected with the qualitative findings, which is under the theme embracing open communication and innovation is important in organization. It is then safe to say that the qualitative data converges quantitative

Engaging with Authority Figures Through Effective Communication. The specific item on informative communication rated as very high is language teachers believe that my superior provides a sufficient amount of useful information that I understand. This result is connected with the qualitative findings, which is under the theme establishing open channels and clear lines of communication. It is then safe to say that the qualitative data converges with quantitative.

Embracing Openness and Collaborative Efforts. The specific item on task-oriented communication rated as very high is language teachers consider that my co-teacher and I readily share important information that is critical to our success. This result is connected with the qualitative findings, which is under the theme embracing open communication and innovation is important in an organization. It is then safe to say that the qualitative data converges with quantitative.

The Significance of Effective Communication Practices. The specific item on task-oriented communication rated as very high is language teachers receive the information I need to effectively perform my job, in most of situations. This result is connected with the qualitative findings, which is under the theme effective information management is essential in organization. It is then safe to say that the qualitative data converges with the quantitative.

Fostering Harmony through Effective Communication. In the quantitative phase, on informative communication about language teachers who see the lines of information are “open” to the principal, all are rated as very high by the respondents. These results are connected with the qualitative findings, which is the nurturing relationship and continuous improvement is possible with effective communication. It is then safe to say that the qualitative data converges with quantitative.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

First, the organizational communication among language teachers is notably robust, characterized by task-oriented communication, informative communication, and a strong grasp of pedagogical knowledge competence. These indicators consistently underscore the efficacy of communication within the language teacher’s organization. Moreover, this suggests a cohesive and productive environment conducive to professional growth and development.

Second, the thematic analysis of qualitative data, derived from in-depth interviews (IDIs), provided deeper pieces of information into language teachers’ experiences of their organizational communication. Through these interviews, various themes emerged, shedding light on the experiences of language teachers. These themes encompassed aspects such as establishing open channels and clear lines of communication, creating – culture of openness and respectful dialogue utilizing effective communication strategies, and addressing miscommunication through collective problem solving.

Furthermore, participants' responses unveiled additional themes, offering further glimpses into language teachers' insights on organizational communication dynamics. These themes emphasized the significance of embracing open communication and innovation is important in organization, effective information management is essential in organization, and nurturing relationships and continuous improvement is possible with effective communication.

Lastly, to comprehensively understand the impact of language teachers' experiences on organizational communication, responses were thematically analyzed to corroborate the quantitative findings. Through this integrated approach, the study confirmed the convergence of quantitative and qualitative results, providing a holistic view of the intricate dynamics within language teaching communities. Notably, both strands of data highlighted the nuanced nature of organizational communication among language teachers, showcasing its mix of negative effects, positive impacts, and overall benefits stemming from their attitudes and practices in organizational communication.

Based on the findings of the study, the following suggestions were made:

Since the level of the language teachers' organizational communication reveals that among the three indicators of organizational communication, informative communication has the lowest mean which affects the organizational communication of the language

teachers, It is recommended that language teachers prioritize a more informative approach to communication to prevent misunderstandings and miscommunication among their colleagues. Specifically, they should cultivate openness to sharing ideas, suggestions, and even constructive criticism from colleagues and supervisors as integral to their professional development. Language teachers should strive to cultivate a significantly improved communication environment to effectively pursue shared goals within their organization and school community. This enhanced communication milieu will foster collaboration, and synergy, and ultimately contribute to the attainment of collective objectives.

Moreover, based on the qualitative phase results on the lived experiences of language teachers about their organizational communication, language teachers should embrace a more open approach to communication, not only with their colleagues but also with their immediate heads or principals. This enables them to share ideas and collaboratively determine what is best for the organization and for the school. Additionally, it's crucial for language teachers to prioritize respect in all communications, as highlighted by participants in the interviews. Integration of diverse communication strategies is also essential to prevent misunderstandings; however, in cases where miscommunication occurs, addressing it through face-to-face conversations or other effective means is imperative.

Furthermore, Effective communication is crucial for language teachers to improve their organizational performance. They must stay informed about upcoming activities, events, and tasks assigned by their supervisors. Clear communication fosters a harmonious environment, allowing collaboration and problem-solving. Language teachers must maintain an open-minded approach, welcoming feedback from both supervisors and colleagues. This continuous improvement of communication methods is vital for organizational growth and goal achievement. By staying informed about school-related matters and directives, language teachers can foster a harmonious environment and contribute to the overall success of their organization.

Lastly, it is also recommended that the immediate head or principal of the school should prioritize keeping their teachers informed and engaged, fostering a sense of belonging within the teacher community rather than merely overseeing them, as suggested by the participant. Through this, teachers will feel empowered to approach their immediate head or principal whenever important matters need to be discussed or school-related issues require immediate attention. Also, the researcher recommends that language teachers should consistently recognize the significance of communication and strive to innovate it to facilitate improved methods of interaction. Communication serves as a vital tool for organizational growth, fostering understanding among all members and creating an open environment conducive to sharing and exchanging thoughts for the betterment of both the organization and the school.

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